

Moths (Lepidoptera) of Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

The world's diversity is not spread equally. Sharp environmental changes may be seen from barren deserts to lush tropical rainforests to lowland forests and alpine pastures. This study was designed to know the diversity of the moth in Dhirkot. The study was conducted from January 2021 to December 2021 to study the Moth fauna at Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. During the research total 25 species of moth were documented, 1.3604 Shanon-weiner Diversity Index was documented from Dhirkot. It is noted that *Corymica pryeri*, *Hyles lineate* and *Clanis Deucalion* are dominant in the study area.

Keywords: Moth, Diversity, Dhirkot, Pakistan

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INTRODUCTION

The world's biodiversity is not spread equally. Sharp environmental changes may be seen from barren deserts to lush tropical rainforests to lowland forests and alpine pastures. Generations of explorers and naturalists have been assembling the early foundations of biogeography for more than two centuries, recording numerous examples of environmental changes along latitude and elevation (Lomolino, 2001). One of the most general ecological interactions is the negative association of species richness with decreasing latitude and rising elevation. They were formerly thought to be caused by a decline in suitable climatic conditions as latitude and elevation decreased. Understanding the patterns and causes of global biodiversity distribution is a critical component of ecological study (Hillebrand, 2004).

However, biodiversity investigations along latitude are among the most difficult and expensive ecological methodologies. Elevation gradients, on the other hand, aggregate substantial variations in climatic conditions across a short geographical range (Körner, 2007). Because elevation gradients are quite common over the world, they soon establish themselves as a viable choice for biogeographical investigations (Rahbek, 2005), offering the possibility to readily investigate the causes of spatial variation in species diversity. The consequences of rising elevation on insects have been thoroughly studied. It has an impact on their morphology, ecology, activity, reproduction, regional distribution, and abundance. The diversity changes with different elevation has provided several possibilities to competently

comprehend the mechanisms involved at small spatial scales, while avoiding misunderstanding between geographical impacts between places (Rasmann *et al.*, 2014).

Biological diversity is vital scientifically (Heyer *et al.*, 2014), socioeconomically (McNeely, 1988), socially (Cilliers, 2010), traditionally (Maffi, 2005; Altaf *et al.*, 2017), aesthetically (Lindemann-Matthies *et al.*, 2010), ethnopharmacologically (Umair *et al.*, 2017; Altaf *et al.*, 2018b; Farooq *et al.*, 2019), educationally (Caro *et al.*, 2003) and also important for “biological control” (Saba *et al.*, 2020) pollutant indicator (Sidra *et al.*, 2019). Diversity is the number of species extant (Altaf *et al.*, 2013; Altaf, 2016). The existing research was intended to know the diversity of the moth in Dhirkot.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was started at January 2018 and end at December 2021 to study the Moth fauna at Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Different methods were applied during surveys and classified into “2 categories”, first “direct field observations” and second “indirect observations” i.e. body parts, carcasses of Moths and meetings with the locals.

STUDY AREA

Dhirkot area is mountainous region of “Azad Jammu and Kashmir” (Bibi *et al.*, 2013; Altaf *et al.*, 2018a; Abbasi *et al.*, 2019; Farooq *et al.*, 2019; Irshad *et al.*, 2019; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Riaz and Altaf, 2021), has various elevation in small region (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of study area (Farooq *et al.*, 2019).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

MS Excel was applied to know diversity of Moth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the research total 25 species of moth were documented, 1.3604 Shannon-weiner Diversity Index was documented from Dhirkot. It is noted that *Corymica pryeri*, *Hyles lineate* and *Clanis Deucalion* are dominant in the study area. It is also noted that increase with elevation, diversity is decreased (Figure 1). The diversity of moths covering a large area of habitat types within a confined region. The findings demonstrated a greatly noteworthy overall link between plant composition and moth community composition, and multivariate analysis suggested that light availability and soil fertility parameters were the habitat features most closely connected to moth community composition. Positive associations between local plant and moth species were also shown to be less robust but still significant. The diversity of plant species in the area was positively connected with moth species richness. That is determined that site conditions and plant composition have a major impact on local moth assemblages (Tyler, 2020).

Table 1: Diversity of Moth in Dhirkot.

Sr.	Names	RA (Pi)	LogPi	PiLogPi
1	<i>Xylophanes tersa</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
2	<i>Spodoptera litura</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
3	<i>Spilosoma luteum</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
4	<i>Nycteola revayana</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
5	<i>Nephelimorpha argentilinea</i>	0.07	-1.176091259	-0.0784
6	<i>Mocis mayeri</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
7	<i>Lymantria todara</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
8	<i>Leucania Phragmitidicola</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
9	<i>Idaea filicata</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
10	<i>Hyles lineate</i>	0.07	-1.176091259	-0.0784
11	<i>Herpetogramma sphingalis</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
12	<i>Hellinsia homodactyla</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
13	<i>Eacles imperialis</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
14	<i>Dysgonia algira</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
15	<i>Drasteria divergens</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
16	<i>Cyclophora packardi</i>	0.07	-1.176091259	-0.0784
17	<i>Costaconvexa centrostrigaria</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
18	<i>Corymica pryeri</i>	0.07	-1.176091259	-0.0784
19	<i>Condica videns</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
20	<i>Cleora sublunaria</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
21	<i>Clanis Deucalion</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
22	<i>Ceratonia undulosa</i>	0.07	-1.176091259	-0.0784
23	<i>Catocala serena</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601

24	<i>Campaea margaritata</i>	0.04	-1.352182518	-0.0601
25	<i>Aloa lactinea</i>	0.02	-1.653212514	-0.0367
	<i>Total</i>	1.00	-9.64327E-17	-1.3604
Shannon-wiener Diversity Index				1.3604

REFERENCES

- Abbasi, A.G.M., S. Nazer, A. Awan, N. Khan, N. Hamid, A.R. Abbasi, M. Altaf. 2019. Assessment of diversity of Butterflies in Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 10-17.
- Altaf, M. 2016. Assessment of Avian and Mammalian Diversity at Selected Sites along river Chenab. University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan.
- Altaf, M., A.G.M. Abbasi, S. Adil. 2021. Anthropogenic impacts on the diversity and distribution of amphibian and reptiles in the vicinity of Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 38-46.
- Altaf, M., A. Javid, Irfan, M.A. Munir, S. Ashraf, K.J. Iqbal, M. Umair. 2013. Diversity, distribution and ecology of birds in summer season at head Khanki, Punjab, Pakistan. *BIOLOGIA (PAKISTAN)*. 59: 131-137.
- Altaf, M., A. Javid, M. Umair, K.J. Iqbal, Z. Rasheed, A.M. Abbasi. 2017. Ethnomedicinal and cultural practices of mammals and birds in the vicinity of river Chenab, Punjab-Pakistan. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 13: 41.
- Altaf, M., S. Nazer, Musarat, I. Manzoor, B. Safeer, S. Yasrub. 2018a. Study of human activities impacts and interaction with small Indian mongoose in Dhirkot, district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 31-37.
- Altaf, M., M. Umair, A.R. Abbasi, N. Muhammad, A.M. Abbasi. 2018b. Ethnomedicinal applications of animal species by the local communities of Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of ethnobiology and ethnomedicine*. 14: 55.
- Bibi, S.S., R.A. Minhas, M.S. Awan, U. Ali, N.I. Dar. 2013. Study of Ethno-Carnivore relationship in Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (Pakistan). *Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences*. 23: 854-859.
- Caro, T., M.B. Mulder, M. Moore. 2003. Effects of conservation education on reasons to conserve biological diversity. *Biological Conservation*. 114: 143-152.
- Cilliers, S. 2010. Social aspects of urban biodiversity—an overview. In: N. Müller, P. Werner & J. Kelcey, *Urban biodiversity and design—implementing the convention on biological diversity in towns and cities*. p 81-100.
- Farooq, A., M.S. Amjad, K. Ahmad, M. Altaf, M. Umair, A.M. Abb. 2019. Ethnomedicinal knowledge of the rural communities of Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 15: 1-45.
- Heyer, R., M.A. Donnelly, M. Foster, R. McDiarmid. 2014. *Measuring and monitoring biological diversity: standard methods for amphibians*. Smithsonian Institution.
- Hillebrand, H. 2004. On the generality of the latitudinal diversity gradient. *The American Naturalist*. 163: 192-211.
- Irshad, A., S.M.H. Gardazi, A. Jadoon. 2019. Analysis of fuel wood extraction pattern for household energy needs in Dhirkot, Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 1-9.
- Körner, C. 2007. The use of ‘altitude’ in ecological research. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*. 22: 569-574.

- Lindemann-Matthies, P., X. Junge, D. Matthies. 2010. The influence of plant diversity on people's perception and aesthetic appreciation of grassland vegetation. *Biological Conservation*. 143: 195-202.
- Lomolino, M.V. 2001. Elevation gradients of species-density: historical and prospective views. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 10: 3-13.
- Maffi, L. 2005. Linguistic, cultural, and biological diversity. *Annu. Rev. Anthropol.* 34: 599-617.
- McNeely, J.A. 1988. Economics and biological diversity: developing and using economic incentives to conserve biological resources. *Iucn*.
- Rahbek, C. 2005. The role of spatial scale and the perception of large-scale species-richness patterns. *Ecology letters*. 8: 224-239.
- Rasmann, S., L. Pellissier, E. Defosse, H. Jactel, G. Kunstler. 2014. Climate-driven change in plant–insect interactions along elevation gradients. *Functional Ecology*. 28: 46-54.
- Riaz, T., M. Altaf. 2021. Diversity and cultural uses of mammals in Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 159-167.
- Saba, M., D.S. Awan, S. Yousaf. 2020. Spider as a biological agent in pest control-A Review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 27-34.
- Sidra, S., R. Saleem, S. Ghafoor, H. Azeem, I. Imtiaz, Z. Parveen. 2019. Fecal matter as a bio-indicator tool for heavy metal pollution. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 1-7.
- Tyler, T. 2020. Relationship between moth (night active Lepidoptera) diversity and vegetation characteristics in southern Sweden. *Journal of Insect Conservation*. 24: 1005-1015.
- Umair, M., M. Altaf, A.M. Abbasi. 2017. An ethnobotanical survey of indigenous medicinal plants in Hafizabad district, Punjab-Pakistan. *PloS one*. 12: e0177912.